

mixture was left for 6 hr. The solid obtained crystallised from acetic acid. The compound was found to be insoluble in dilute alkali and did not give an acetoxy derivative. M.p. 206°. (Found : C, 75.25 ; H, 5.39. $C_{16}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 75.56 ; H, 5.51%). IR (nujol) cm^{-1} : 1730 (CO). NMR ($CDCl_3$) (ppm) : 8.3–8.1 (2H, m, due to H-5 and H-8), 7.72–7.52 (2H, m, due to H-6 and H-7), 6.7 (1H, s, due to H-3), 6.3 (1H, s, due to H-3'), 4.22 (2H, q, due to OCH_2CH_3), 2.46 (3H, s, due to $-CH_3-4'$) and 1.6 (3H, t, due to $-OCH_2CH_3$).

The de-ethylation of this product with anhydrous aluminium chloride in benzene gave a product, whose m.p. and mixed m.p. with 4-hydroxy-4'-methyl naphtho (1,2 : 6',5') α -pyrone was 286°. On ethylation with diethyl sulphate in dry acetone and anhydrous potassium carbonate it gave Buu Hoi's product m.p. 206°.

4-Hydroxy-2'-methyl naphtho (1,2 : 6',5') γ -pyrone :

A mixture of 1,4-dihydroxy naphthalene (1.5 g.) in diphenyl ether (12 ml.) and ethyl acetoacetate (4g.) was refluxed for 2.1/2 hr. Petroleum ether was added to the reaction mixture after cooling. The solid obtained was soluble in dilute alkali. It crystallised from dimethyl formamide in tiny needles (0.5 g.), m.p. 315°. (Found : C, 74.04 ; H, 4.03. $C_{14}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 74.33 ; H, 4.42%).

1,4-Dihydroxy-2-acetyl naphthalene : The above γ -pyrone derivative (0.5 g) was refluxed with sodium hydroxide (20 ml. ; 20%) for 30 minutes. The mixture was cooled, diluted and acidified. The separated product crystallised from benzene, m. p. 215°. Mixed m. p. with 1,4-dihydroxy-2-acetyl naphthalene prepared as follows was not depressed.

1,4-Dihydroxy naphthalene was acetylated as usual and the mixture of 1,4-diacetoxy naphthalene (2 g.) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (6 g.) was heated at 140° for 3 hr. On working as usual the product crystallised from benzene. It gave wine red colour with alcoholic ferric chloride and was soluble in alkali. It analysed for monoacetyl compound. M.P. 215°. Yield 0.5 g. (Found : C, 71.61 ; H, 4.73. $C_{12}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 71.29 ; 4.94%).

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Synthesis and Biological Activity of Some New N⁺ 3(2 phenyl quinazolin(3H)-4-one) Acyl Hydrazones

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SEVERAL new hydrazone derivatives have been synthesised by the condensation of 3(2-phenyl-quinazolin (3H)-4-one) acyl hydrazides with substituted aromatic aldehydes. All of these were screened for their antibacterial and insecticidal activities.

During recent years many workers have emphasized the bactericidal¹, herbicidal², insecticidal³ and fungicidal⁴ properties of various hydrazones. Several quinazolone derivatives have been shown to possess anticonvulsant^{5,6} and insecticidal⁷ properties. Keeping these important observations in view, some 3(2-phenyl quinazolin (3H)-4-one) acyl hydrazones have been synthesised to study their bactericidal and insecticidal properties.

I, X = OC_2H_5

II, X = $NHNH_2$

III, X = $NH-N=CHC_6H_4R$

The structure of the compounds were supported by elemental analysis, melting points, t.l.c. and infrared spectroscopy.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Infrared spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer which tally with those in literature.

The key intermediates I and II were prepared by the esterification of 3-(2-phenylquinazolin (3H)-4-one) alkanolic acid (which were prepared by the interaction of benzoxazinone with different amino acids) and then treatment with hydrazine hydrate respectively⁸.

N-3(2-phenylquinazolin (3H)-4-one) acyl hydrazones (III): To 3(2-phenyl-quinazolin (3H) 4-one) acyl hydrazide (0.01 mol) in ethanol (20 ml), an ethanolic solution of appropriate aromatic aldehydes (0.01 mole) were added. The reaction mixture was heated under reflux for 3-4 hours and the solid mass separated on cooling was crystallised from ethanol.

Biological activity: These newly synthesised hydrazones were tested for their antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus subtilis* by agar plate diffusion technique⁹ and insecticidal activity against adult male and female cockroaches using microsyringe method¹⁰.

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA AND BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITIES OF THE HYDRAZONES (III)

Sl. No.	R	M.P.	Antibacterial Activity, Insecticidal activity against				
			<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	K. D. time (hrs) % 0.5	Concentration 0.1	
1.	1	4-NH ₂	178	++	+	15	17.5
2.	1	3-NO ₂	191	—	+	15.5	17.5
3.	1	4-Cl	158	+++	++	13.5	16.0
4.	1	4-NO ₂	240	—	—	17	20
5.	1	4-N < CH ₃ CH ₃	185	—	—	17	21
6.	1	4-NO ₂	245	+	++	14	16.5
7.	1	H	215	+	+	16	17.5
8.	1	2-Cl	185	++	—	17.5	18.5
9.	1	2,4-Di-Cl	221	+++	++	14.5	18
10.	1	2-OH-5NO ₂	295	—	—	18	22
11.	1	4-N < C ₆ H ₅ C ₆ H ₅	182	—	—	16	18.5
11.	1	2,4-Di-OCH ₃	173	+	+	16	19.5
12.	1	4-OCH ₃	129	+	+	15	18.0
14.	1	—CH=CH	140	—	—	14	15.0
15.	2	4-NH ₂	211	+++	+++	14.0	16.5
16.	2	3-NO ₂	182	—	++	17	19
17.	2	4-Cl	200	+	+	14	17
18.	2	4-OH	130	—	—	16	23
19.	2	3-N < CH ₃ CH ₃	250	++	++	16	21
20.	2	4-N < C ₆ H ₅ C ₆ H ₅	156	—	—	17	19.5
21.	2	2,4-di-OCH ₃	190	+++	++	14	15.5
22.	2	4-NO ₂	210	—	—	15	17.5

— = No inhibition
 + = Zone size 5-8 mm.
 ++ = Zone size 8-14 mm;
 +++ = Zone size above 15 mm.

Control 0.5% 0.1%
 Parathione 4 4.5
 Acetone 40 40

All the compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

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Preliminary Investigation on the Structure of *Woodfordia fruticosa* Gum

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THE stem of the plant *Woodfordia fruticosa* (Linn.) Kurz. Syn. *Woodfordia floribunda* Salisb. (Fam. *Lythraceae*), when broken exudes a pale yellow gum locally called as 'Dhau Gum'. It finds extensive application¹ in textile printing as it can protect parts of fabric which can not be coloured during the process of dyeing. Since *Woodfordia fruticosa* gum has remained uninvestigated so far, the present work has been undertaken to isolate the gum polysaccharide in an homogeneous state for elucidation of its structure.

Crude gum was obtained as a flocculant white precipitate by treating an aqueous, acidified solution of the commercial product with large excess of ethanol. Repeated fractional precipitation followed by treatment with cation and anion exchange resins yielded the pure

polysaccharide in the form of white powder m.p. 223-25°(dec.), $(\alpha)_D^{20} = +40.69^\circ$, (Ash, 0.34 per cent). Upon paper electrophoresis it migrated as a single spot ($\mu = 0.034 \times 10^{-8}$ cm², sec⁻¹, volt⁻¹) thereby establishing the homogeneity of the sample. Pure gum is non-reducing in nature and is free from nitrogen, sulphur, halogen and methoxyl. It gave on analysis Furfural, 11.46; Pentoses, 22.55; Anhydrouronic acid, 10.75 percent and Eq. wt. (by titration) 2177. Acetylation² of the polysaccharide furnished a crystalline acetyl derivative m.p. 170-172° (-OAc, 45.53 percent).

Complete acid hydrolysis of the pure gum with sulphuric acid (2*N*) for 40 hrs. on a steam bath produced a mixture of neutral sugars (A) and barium salt of uronic acid (B) in the form of a brown powder. Paper chromatography of (A) showed the presence of D-galactose, L-arabinose and L-rhamnose (very weak spot). All the three sugars were obtained in a crystalline state by cellulose column chromatography³, and finally identified from their specific rotations and the m.p.s. of their characteristic crystalline derivatives. Quantitative acid hydrolysis of the gum revealed that the two major sugars, D-galactose and L-arabinose, were present in a ratio of 3 : 1. (B) was identified as D-galacturonic acid from its colour reactions, migration rate and also from its conversion to D-galactose⁴.

Upon graded hydrolysis with dilute sulphuric acid (0.1 *N*) on a steam bath for 9 hrs, the gum yielded a mixture of neutral oligosaccharides (C) and barium salt of poligouronic acids besides galactose and arabinose. Chromatography of (C) on a charcoal-celite column⁵ failed to produce the individual oligosaccharide in a homogeneous state. The mixture of oligosaccharides was finally separated by preparative partition chromatography on Whatman No. 3 mm. paper sheets. The degree of polymerisation of different homogeneous components was estimated according to the method of Peat, Whelan and Roberts⁶. Thus two disaccharides, one trisaccharide, one tetrasaccharide and one pentasaccharide were finally obtained from fraction (C). Their characteristic properties are given in table-1

TABLE 1

Sl. No.	Nature of Oligosaccharides	Recellobiose value in ethyl acetate : acetic acid : butanol : water (4 : 3 : 2 : 2)	Specific rotation $(\alpha)_D^{20}$ in water	Degree of Polymerisation
1.	Disaccharide	1.66	+ 29.89°	1.89
2.	Disaccharide	1.41	+ 31.65°	1.80
3.	Trisaccharide	0.48	+123.35°	3.04
4.	Tetrasaccharide	0.14	+197.16°	4.03
5.	Pentasaccharide	0.04	—	4.85

Further studies on the structure of *Woodfordia fruticosa* gum and in progress.